

Training in EOSC Future project

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CESSDA ERIC

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

22 member and 1 observer countries

MISSION

- to provide a sustainable research infrastructure that enables the research community to conduct high-quality research in the social sciences
- to contribute to effective solutions to the major challenges facing society today.

● Members (22) / Observers (1)
● Partners (12)

1. Austria
2. Belgium
3. Croatia
4. Czech Republic
5. Denmark
6. Finland
7. France
8. Germany
9. Greece
10. Hungary
11. Iceland
12. Ireland
13. North Macedonia
14. Netherlands
15. Norway
16. Portugal
17. Serbia
18. Slovak Republic
19. Slovenia
20. Sweden
21. Switzerland (Observer)
22. UK
23. Italy

Countries aiming at membership:

- Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Bulgaria
- Estonia
- Lithuania
- Poland
- Romania
- Spain

EOSC Future approach

EOSC Future will provide a user-friendly environment for:

Data discovery

Data storage

Data recomposition

Computing services

Complex workflows

Integratable services

EOSC Future is structured around six thematic pillars:

Policy and strategy

Technology and interoperability

Excellent science

Co-development and procurement

Skills and training

User engagement

Skills and Training

To train both users and providers to make the most of the EOSC environment, the project will establish an EOSC Knowledge Hub. The Hub will build a network of expert trainers, and catalogue existing support materials while developing new training courses and documents.

Skills & Training Objectives

Train stakeholders to become active users and providers of EOSC and increase uptake of resources, and Open Science.

Support providers to add their resources in the EOSC Portal and work with the INFRAEOSC-07 projects and Science Clusters to support users.

Consolidate the emerging cross-discipline trainer community (including the INFRAEOSC-07 projects) to avoid duplication of effort, focusing on key components of interoperability, service offering, and data provision.

Build and operate a learning management system and training catalogue as integral parts of the EOSC Portal to sustain the EOSC Knowledge Hub.

Learning Resources Development and Delivery

Source: Venkataraman, S.: Building training and its infrastructure for EOOSC, EOOSC Symposium 2023

Learning Paths

- EOSC Institutional Facilitator
- EOSC Resource Provider
- EOSC User Trainer
- EOSC Research Practitioner
- EOSC Citizen Science Practitioner
- EOSC Accelerator

Source: Venkataraman, S.: Building training and its infrastructure for EOSC, EOSC Symposium 2023

Community of Practice of Open Science Training Coordinators

Quality assurance criteria for learning resources

CREATION OF LEARNING RESOURCES

QA criteria and procedures focus on the quality of the learning resources that are being produced

A content creator persona

SELECTION OF LEARNING RESOURCES

(select/accept learning resources in a training platform or a catalogue of learning resources)

QA criteria and procedures focus on the quality of the materials to be included, but the main goal is to ensure the quality of the platform/catalogue.

A content selector persona

METADATA RECORDS CREATION

(e.g. during the curation of records in a training platform/catalogue)

QA criteria and procedures focus on the quality of the records in the platform/catalogue (metadata, etc.), where the main goal is to ensure the quality of the platform/catalogue.

A metadata creator for the content persona

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7520222>

January 2023

www.openaire.eu/cop-training

**TRAINING MODULE: STREAMLINING
THE ONBOARDING TO THE SERVICE
CATALOGUE USING APIS**

25/01/2023 - 10:00 - 11:30 CET

[Read more](#)

**TRAINING WORKSHOP:
PROTOTYPING PRIVACY POLICY &
TERMS OF USE DOCUMENTATION
FOR THE EOSC PORTAL**

23/01/2023 - 11.00-12.30 CET

[Read more](#)

**TRAINING: HOW TO WRITE PRIVACY
POLICY AND TERMS OF USE
DOCUMENTATION FOR THE EOSC
PORTAL**

7/12/2022 - 10 - 11.30 CET

[Read more](#)

**WEBINAR: PAN-EUROPEAN DIGITAL
ASSETS SUPPORTING RESEARCH
COMMUNITIES – BENEFITS &
OPPORTUNITIES**

5/12/2022 - 6/12/2022 - 09:00 - 13:00

[Read more](#)

**WEBINAR: RDA/EOSC FUTURE CALL
FOR INTEROPERABILITY
FRAMEWORK CONTRIBUTIONS**

24/11/2022 - 11:00 - 12:00 CET

[Read more](#)

**TRAIN-THE-TRAINER: AN ACTIVE
LEARNING COURSE ON
UNDERSTANDING & USING EOSC**

21/11/2022 - 24/11/2022

[Read more](#)

EOSC SYMPOSIUM 2022

14/11/2022 - 17/11/2022

[Read more](#)

**SERVICE DOCUMENTATION FOR
EOSC PROVIDERS WORKSHOP 1:
DESCRIBING YOUR SERVICE FOR
ONBOARDING**

9/11/2022 - 13:00-15:00 CET

[Read more](#)

**NATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURES IN
EOSC**

11/10/2022 - 12/10/2022

[Read more](#)

What is the EOSC Knowledge Hub (KH)?

- Composed of a:
 - Learning resource catalogue
 - Learning platform
- Community resource for all things related to EOSC training (and not just EOSC Future!)
- Initial specification completed through a deliverable
- It is aimed at the five principal actors

Source: Venkataraman, S.: Building training and its infrastructure for EOSC, EOSC Symposium 2023

Workflow

www.openplato.eu

Source: Venkataraman, S.: Building training and its infrastructure for EOSC, EOSC Symposium 2023

Training resources Catalogue metadata specification

Metadata set for Existing Resources (for the first harvesting process)

Metadata set for New materials (for registrations directly in the catalogue)

- The RDA minimal metadata for learning resources set was then taken as an initial reference
- An EOSC-customized version of that set was created.
 - This EOSC-customized set soon appeared not to address in full the concerns of the community
 - it proved to be quite restrictive with regard to the onboarding of existing resources,
 - a series of meetings with the identified Pilot Catalogues (ELIXIR TeSS, SSH Training Discovery Toolkit, DARIAH Campus, EOSC-Pillar) were therefore organized to validate the initial metadata set and compare the solutions adopted by various projects.

[Training Catalogue - Minimal Metadata for Learning Resources - EOSC Future Public - Wiki EOSC Future](#)

Minimal Metadata for Learning Resources

New records

onboarding of resources by Providers directly in the catalogue

Name	Definition	Type	Usage notes, allowed values, examples, other constraints
Title	The human readable name of the learning resource.	TEXT (1000)	<p>Notes: It should be transcribed from the learning resource itself or the descriptive metadata found on the resource landing page. If no title exists, the provider should create it. If the resource exists in more than one language, a separate record should be created for that version.</p> <p>Allowed values: Should be Unicode and allow for diacritics.</p> <p>Example: "CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide"</p> <p>Constraints: Not repeatable</p>
Abstract/Description	A brief synopsis about or description of the learning resource.	TEXT (2000)	<p>Notes: The description can include the relationship of this resource to others, if applicable, e.g., a part within a series or collection, and the existence of translations of the resource into other languages.</p> <p>Allowed values: Should be Unicode and allow for diacritics</p> <p>Example: "A guide designed by European experts to help social science researchers make their research data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR)."</p> <p>Constraints: Not repeatable</p>
Author(s)	The name of entity(ies) authoring the resource.	TEXT	<p>Notes: Authors should be listed in the order presented on the resource or on the descriptive metadata on the landing page of the resource. Multiple authors should be listed with commas between the names. Names should include given or first name and family or surname, and a personal identifier such as an ORCID, if available. Some input systems may offer separate fields for each of these identifying items.</p> <p>Allowed values: Should be Unicode and allow for diacritics</p> <p>Example: "CESSDA Training Team"</p> <p>Constraints: Repeatable</p>
Primary Language	The language in which the resource was originally published or made available.	TEXT (2)	<p>Notes: If the resource exists in more than one language, that information can be included in the Abstract/Description term. A second record should be created, if possible, for the other language versions of the resource.</p> <p>Allowed values: String composed by a code as defined by the code set ISO 639-1:2002</p> <p>Example: "en"</p> <p>Constraints: Not repeatable</p>
Keyword(s)	The keyword(s) or tag(s) used to describe the resource.	TEXT (100)	<p>Notes: Keywords may be single words or phrases that characterize what the resource is about. Ideally, the keywords come from a controlled vocabulary of terms that are curated and structured to represent the specific nature of the collection of learning resources, e.g., by subject domain, data format and/or data type. In a web or searchable catalogue / web environment for learning resources,</p>

Existing Resources

Aggregation from training catalogues

Metadata Field	Mandatory	Recommended (info that if not provided will limit the use of the resource)	Optional
Title	Y		
Description		Y	
Author (s)	Y It must be filled with something. It will come prefilled with the name of the training service provider and it can be updated adding the name of the author		
Language (different resources for different languages)	Y		
Keywords		Y (alert)	
License		Y Extremely relevant for us. Not mandatory field but if the training provider misses on this information will make hard to have further uses of the resources	
Access Rights (open, closed, restricted, with a cost, etc.)	Y		
Version Date(s)	Y		
URL to resource	Y		
Resource URL type			Y
Target Group (Audience)	Y (controlled vocabulary)		
Learning Resource Type		Y (Use controlled vocabulary provided by DCMI on the LRMI initiative: https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/lrmi/concept_schemes/learningResourceType/) By learning resource we mean a persistent resource that has one or more physical or digital representation, and that explicitly involves, specifies or entails a learning activity or learning experience).	
Learning Outcome	Y (controlled vocabulary)		

EOSC Training Resource Profile - Data Model

- Basic Information
 - Detailed & access Information
 - **Learning Information**
 - Geographical and Language Availability Information
 - Classification Information
- +
- Contact Information
 - **Code Lists, Taxonomies, Classifications**

<https://wiki.eoscfuture.eu/display/PUBLIC/EOSC+Training+Resource+Profile+--+Data+Model>

Training Catalog

https://search.eosc-portal.eu/search/training?q=*

ALL CATALOGS PUBLICATIONS DATA SOFTWARE SERVICES DATA SOURCES **TRAININGS** OTHER

Filters

Research step clear all

Access Training Material (77)

Access right clear all

Open access (76)

Resource type clear all

Search in resource type...

- Lesson Plan (62)
- Activity Plan (48)
- Assessment (45)
- Recorded Lesson (21)
- Other (5)
- Supporting Document (5)
- Course (3)
- Training materials (1)
- Workshop (1)
- lesson (1)

show more

77 search results in Trainings

Training Open Access CC BY 4.0 English

Introduction to Persistent Identifiers

Open access 📅 🔗 Type: training

Authors: Kálman, Tibor

Resource type: Recorded Lesson

Content type: Video

📌 [Data management](#) [EOSC](#) [Open Science](#)

As part of the DARIAH Friday Frontiers in-house webinar series Dr. Tibor Kálman (GWDG) gives an introduction to Persistent Identifiers. Why do we need them how do we apply them and how do (digital) arts and humanities scholars benefit from them in pa...

Show more

Training Open Access CC BY 4.0 English

EOSC Architecture

Open access 📅 🔗 Type: training

Authors: Tenhunen, Ville Chen, Yin Provost, Lottie Di Donato, Francesca

Resource type: Recorded Lesson

Content type: Video

📌 [Open Science](#) [EOSC](#)

Suggested

Open Science is Just Good Science

Training Open Access

English

Author names: Tennant, Jon

R for Reproducible Scientific Analysis

Training Open Access

English Spanish

Author names: Capes, Gerard Deppen, Jacob Jiménez, Verónica Pereyra, Silvana Salgado, Heladia

Crafting your own training using EOSC resources

Training Open Access

English

Author names: Bezuidenhout, Louise Clare, Helen Dijk, Elly Ferguson, Kim Flohr, Pascal Hirsch, Lisa Kuchma, Iryna Ševkušić, Milica Vipavc Brvar, Irena EOSC Future

Outlook and Lessons learned

- Training has to be oriented at actors' needs
- Be as flexible as possible, but follow standards
- Generating training material is an iterative and dynamic process
- Contribution and support from all stakeholders is essential
- Feedback from trainees and trainers serve as proposals for improving EOSC portal

Get in touch

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Disclaimer: Slides about EOSC Future project were prepared by projects' communication team

